

Derivatives of *m*-Cresotic Acid.

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Schleussner and Voswinckel (*Annalen*, 1921, 422, 111) reported that chloral condensed with *m*-cresotic acid in the *meta* position to the hydroxyl group. Although in their products the *para* position, which is surely not unfavourable to condensation, is supposed to be vacant, they were unable to carry the condensation beyond the first stage.

It is now found by the present authors that chloral condenses with 4-hydroxy-5-carboxy-2-methylmandelic acid (I, R=H) (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 266) and with its methyl ether (I, R=Me) (Meldrum and Alimchandani, *ibid.*, 1929, 6, 256).

The hydroxy condensation product could not be purified; the methyl ether product has been purified, analysed and further examined. It might have the constitution (V) or (VII) if *m*-cresotic acid and its derivatives have any tendency to condense with chloral in the *meta* position to the hydroxyl or methoxyl group. The constitution (V) is out of consideration because the substance, when heated with sulphuric acid, does not give the aldehyde (VI). The constitution (VII) is wrong because the substance (a) on hydrolysis, gives the original mandelic acid (I, R=Me), (b) on reduction, gives the substance (III, R=Me) which on treatment with sulphuric acid gives 2-methyl-4-methoxy-5-carboxybenzaldehyde (IV, R=Me) (Meldrum and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*), (c) on oxidation, gives *α*-coccinic acid and not cochinillic acid. Thus the evidence is that chloral does not condense with *m*-cresotic acid or its derivatives in the *meta* position to the hydroxyl group.

All the reactions indicate that the condensation product is the chloralide (II, R=Me). The reduction product (III) is a mixed ether in which one of the radicals is derived from the alcohol HO·CH₂·CHCl₂. There is a possibility of a double bond in the side-chain of (III) of the type -CH:CCl₂. But this has been excluded on the grounds (i) of the results of analysis and (ii) that it does not

absorb bromine. Meldrum and Kapadia (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 483) have also described similar reduction products containing the group $-\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$.

Other ethers obtained similarly from various chloralides and derived from the alcohol $-\text{HO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$ will be described in a subsequent paper.

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(I)

(II)

(IV)

(III)

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-2-methylmandelic acid chloralide (II, R = Me).—4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-2-methylmandelic acid (I, R = Me) (10 g.), chloral hydrate (14 g.) and sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) were mixed and the clear solution, obtained on shaking, was kept for 5-6 days. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice when a white solid separated, which was collected, washed and dried on a porous plate. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate as rhombic crystals, m.p. 178-79°. (Found: Cl, 28.91. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 28.81 per cent). It is very soluble in acetic acid, acetone, ether; soluble in ethyl acetate, chloroform and petrol.

Hydrolysis of the chloralide.—The chloralide (3 g.) was boiled with a solution of barium hydroxide (10 g. in 150 c.c. of water) for about an hour. The solution, when evaporated to a small bulk, deposited silky clusters of needles which were found to be the barium salt of the original mandelic acid (I).

Reduction of the chloralide.—To the hot solution of the chloralide (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.), zinc dust was added slowly. After the reduction was over, the solution was filtered to remove unchanged zinc and the filtrate was diluted with water. On rubbing with a glass rod, a white substance was obtained which was found to be a zinc salt. On treating with hydrochloric acid, the reduction product was obtained. It crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol as needles, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: C, 45.94; H, 4.00; Cl, 21.27. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6Cl_2$ requires C, 46.30; H, 4.16; Cl, 21.04 per cent. Unsaturated formula $C_{13}H_{12}O_6Cl_2$ requires C, 46.58; H, 3.58; Cl, 21.17 per cent).

The reduction product (III, 1 g) was dissolved in chloroform and bromine (0.5 g.) dissolved in the same solvent, was added. The colour of the bromine was not discharged even on keeping for 24 hours, indicating that the reduction product was a saturated substance. On evaporating the solvent, the original product was obtained. Dry ether was substituted as a solvent with the same result.

Action of sulphuric acid on the reduction product.—The reduction product (1 g.) was heated with 20 c.c. of sulphuric acid on the water-bath; hydrochloric acid gas was evolved. On adding the cold reaction mixture to water, a white substance separated, which after crystallising from water was found to be identical with 4-methoxy-5-carboxy-2-methylbenzaldehyde (IV, R=Me) (Meldrum and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*).

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